

Solvate Suite Part II: A Complete and Modular Software for Molecular Modeling of Microsolvation with Sequential Multiscale Approach

Additional Examples

Application Examples

Integration with ORCA Program

Aqueous Systems: Example of Dimethylamine in Water (Two Oxidation States)

Despite the short simulation time in the equilibration and production stages presented in a previous article, it is possible to identify significant hydrogen bond structures, as shown in Figure 1. This analysis, performed by Solvate through HBOND module, returns fully optimized structures (no imaginary frequencies) at GFN2-xTB level.

Figure 1: Example of hydrogen bonds identified by Solvate in water solvent. In (a) there is only one proton-donating hydrogen bond, which is consistent with the reduction of the localized electron density in nitrogen as a function of the cationic state. In (b) there are two hydrogen bonds, a proton donor to a water molecule, and a proton acceptor to a water molecule. In all cases, the structures were fully optimized at the GFN2-xTB level until the complete removal of imaginary frequencies.

Non-Aqueous Systems: Example of Methanesulfonic Acid in DMSO (Two Protonation States)

In this example, whose equilibration and production process were described in a previous article, the analysis of hydrogen bonds performed by *Solvate* enabled the identification of only one structure in the acid state (Figure 2). As in the previous example, this structure was returned by the program module fully optimized.

Figure 2: Example of hydrogen bonds identified by *Solvate* in DMSO solvent. As expected, a hydrogen bond was identified only in the acidic state. In this case, only one hydrogen bond structure was identified in the protonated state. The structure was fully optimized at the GFN2-xTB level.

Integration with GROMACS Program

Aqueous System: Pyridinol in Water

Table 1: Statistical parameters of pyridinol in water obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.2269	0.1943	307.2484
Temperature (K)	298.1624	0.0024	3.8419
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9992	0.0000	0.0057
Short-Range (ua)	-152.2085	0.0104	16.4835
Potential (ua)	-35.6931	0.0001	0.1164
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	4.6760		

Table 2: Statistical parameters of pyridinol in water obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2545 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0005	0.0045	0.2295
Temperature (K)	298.1264	0.0754	3.8050
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9992	0.0001	0.0051
Short-Range (ua)	-152.6673	0.3267	16.4835
Potential (ua)	-35.6935	0.0023	0.1167
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.8600		

Chart 1: Labels used to identify reference and selected atoms in RDF analysis of the pyridinol in water.

Chart 2: RDF analysis between the oxygen and nitrogen reference atoms of the pyridinol and the selected water oxygen for the full trajectory (generated and analyzed by GROMACS) and for the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The vertical dotted line highlights the distance at which the cumulative value reached the number of solvent molecules selected for clusters extraction and characterization.

Full Trajectory

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 3: RDF analysis between the centers of mass of the solute and solvent molecules in the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The data indicate that 55 molecules correspond to all the molecules in the first solvation shell and part of the second shell.

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 4: Distribution of RMSDs (in Å) per cluster obtained after optimization with the FCA and FCR methods. In the FCA case, the RMSD values consistently remain below 0.10 Å. With the FCR procedure, the primary contributions to the RMSD come from the solute, which can be attributed to the additional optimization step where the solute is optimized at the DFT level within the fixed solvent cavity.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 5: Distribution of SCF and Gibbs free energies per cluster (relative to the lowest energy cluster) obtained after optimization with FCA and FCR methods. In the FCA case, the thermal contributions to the free energy come from the entire cluster with the SPH method, obtained at *xTB-GFN2/ALPB* level. In contrast, with the FCR procedure, the thermal contributions originate solely from the solute at the DFT/PCM level with the partial Hessian method. This accounts for the larger disparities between the SCF and Gibbs energies in this method.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 6: Distribution of Gibbs free energies (relative to the lowest energy cluster) for selected clusters in an energy window of 30 kcal·mol⁻¹. The greater number of structures in the FCA case results from the smaller structural deformations observed in the optimization process.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 7: Stochastic SCF and Gibbs free energies for 100 selected clusters and optimized with FCA method.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Single Point Energies

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

Note: The first result was obtained in the first stage of GCALC execution (SCF energies), when all structures extracted from the trajectory were characterized at the xTB-FF level (i.e., with low computational cost). Therefore, the SCF energy can be used as an estimate to determine the minimum number of clusters to obtain free energy convergence.

Chart 8: Stochastic Gibbs free energies for selected 100 clusters and optimized with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation: Gibbs Free Energies

Note: It is important to highlight that the behavior of the stochastic average is quite similar between the two optimization procedures.

Non-Aqueous System: Pyridinol in DMSO

Table 3: Statistical parameters of pyridinol in DMSO obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0633	0.1658	262.1981
Temperature (K)	298.1846	0.0012	1.9233
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1258	0.0000	0.0029
Short-Range (ua)	-169.0906	0.0070	11.0047
Potential (ua)	-103.9161	0.0001	0.1808
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.7590		

Table 4: Statistical parameters of pyridinol in DMSO obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 3101 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	0.9973	0.0042	0.2325
Temperature (K)	298.2210	0.0347	1.9318
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1258	0.0000	0.0027
Short-Range (ua)	-169.0934	0.2002	11.1508
Potential (ua)	-103.9148	0.0033	0.1818
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.3400		

Chart 9: Labels used to identify reference and selected atoms in RDF analysis of the pyridinol in DMSO.

Chart 10: RDF analysis between the nitrogen reference atom of the pyridinol and the selected DMSO sulfur and oxygen atoms for the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The vertical dotted line highlights the distance at which the cumulative value reached the number of solvent molecules selected for clusters extraction and characterization. The data indicate that 38 molecules correspond to all the molecules in the first and the second solvation shell.

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 11: Distribution of RMSDs (in Å) per cluster obtained after optimization with the FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 12: Distribution of SCF and Gibbs free energies per cluster (relative to the lowest energy cluster) obtained after optimization with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 13: Distribution of Gibbs free energies (relative to the lowest energy cluster) for selected clusters in an energy window of 30 kcal·mol⁻¹.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 14: Stochastic SCF and Gibbs free energies for 100 selected clusters and optimized with FCA method.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Single Point Energies

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

Chart 15: Stochastic Gibbs free energies for selected 100 clusters and optimized with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation: Gibbs Free Energies

Non-Aqueous System: Methylfuran in Acetone

Table 5: Statistical parameters of methylfuran in acetone obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0737	0.1869	295.4745
Temperature (K)	298.1934	0.0012	1.9338
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.8428	0.0000	0.0030
Short-Range (ua)	-75.6242	0.0048	7.5497
Potential (ua)	-71.0858	0.0001	0.1738
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	7.0230		

Table 6: Statistical parameters of methylfuran in acetone obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2581 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	0.9970	0.0045	0.2295
Temperature (K)	298.2321	0.0379	1.9238
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.8427	0.0001	0.0029
Short-Range (ua)	-75.5348	0.1503	7.6377
Potential (ua)	-71.0815	0.0035	0.1763
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	6.6420		

Chart 16: Labels used to identify reference and selected atoms in RDF analysis of the methylfuran in acetone.

Chart 17: RDF analysis between the carbon and oxygen reference atoms of the methylfuran and the selected acetone carbon and oxygen atoms for the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The vertical dotted line highlights the distance at which the cumulative value reached the number of solvent molecules selected for clusters extraction and characterization.

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 18: RDF analysis between the centers of mass of the solute and solvent molecules in the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The data indicate that 46 molecules correspond to all the molecules in the first and the second solvation shells.

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 19: Distribution of RMSDs (in Å) per cluster obtained after optimization with the FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 20: Distribution of SCF and Gibbs free energies per cluster (relative to the lowest energy cluster) obtained after optimization with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 21: Distribution of Gibbs free energies (relative to the lowest energy cluster) for selected clusters in an energy window of $30 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 22: Stochastic SCF and Gibbs free energies for 100 selected clusters and optimized with FCA method.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Single Point Energies

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

Chart 23: Stochastic Gibbs free energies for selected 100 clusters and optimized with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation: Gibbs Free Energies

Non-Aqueous System: Methylfuran in chloroform

Table 7: Statistical parameters of methylfuran in chloroform obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0715	0.1346	212.8249
Temperature (K)	298.1764	0.0016	2.5396
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.4850	0.0000	0.0062
Short-Range (ua)	-65.5245	0.0046	7.3183
Potential (ua)	-13.7499	0.0001	0.1405
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	4.6220		

Table 8: Statistical parameters of methylfuran in chloroform obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 3780 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	0.9985	0.0037	0.2300
Temperature (K)	298.2221	0.0411	2.5286
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.4849	0.0001	0.0060
Short-Range (ua)	-65.6814	0.1181	7.2629
Potential (ua)	-13.7463	0.0022	0.1369
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	4.3150		

Chart 24: Labels used to identify reference and selected atoms in RDF analysis of the methylfuran in chloroform.

Chart 25: RDF analysis between the carbon reference atom of the methylfuran and the selected chloroform carbon and chlorine atoms for the truncated trajectory (extracted and analyzed by Solvate). The vertical dotted line highlights the distance at which the cumulative value reached the number of solvent molecules selected for clusters extraction and characterization. The data indicate that 28 molecules correspond to all the molecules in the first and the second solvation shells.

Extracted Trajectory

Chart 26: Distribution of RMSDs (in Å) per cluster obtained after optimization with the FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Note: the specific case of the high RMSD value of the solute in structure 6 is due to its high mobility within the solvent cavity (in this case, the optimization led to the solute exiting the cavity), which is reflected in the high relative energy (see the graph below).

Chart 27: Distribution of SCF and Gibbs free energies per cluster (relative to the lowest energy cluster) obtained after optimization with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 28: Distribution of Gibbs free energies (relative to the lowest energy cluster) for selected clusters in an energy window of $30 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation

Chart 29: Stochastic SCF and Gibbs free energies for 100 selected clusters and optimized with FCA method.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Single Point Energies

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

Chart 30: Stochastic Gibbs free energies for selected 100 clusters and optimized with FCA and FCR methods.

FCA - Full Cluster Accommodated Geometry: Gibbs Free Energies

FCR - Full Cluster Geometry Relaxation: Gibbs Free Energies

